

Space-Based ISR: A Modern Imperative in Defence

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Abstract

Space-based Intelligence Surveillance & Reconnaissance (ISR) plays a crucial role in modern military operations, providing unique capabilities that enhance situational awareness across strategic, operational, and tactical levels. This paper explores the significance of space ISR, emphasizing its operational value and technological advancements. By leveraging the distinct properties of the space domain, ISR systems enable comprehensive monitoring and intelligence gathering, which are essential for effective decision-making in complex environments. The integration of advanced technologies and the collaboration between government and commercial entities further enhance the effectiveness and efficiency of space ISR. As military operations increasingly rely on information dominance, the role of space ISR becomes indispensable in addressing contemporary security challenges and ensuring national defense.

Keywords

Space ISR, situational awareness, remote sensing, OODA loop, geospatial intelligence, information dominance

1. Introduction

Space ISR stands here for the military function of Intelligence Surveillance & Reconnaissance (ISR), as performed through space-based systems. Such space systems offer, multi-potent, remote sensing platforms that operate from near Earth orbits to empower the distinct capacity of space ISR.

The space domain has introduced unique operational qualities into ISR that support critically the strategic, operational and, lately also, the tactical level of military activities, both in peacetime and warfare.

By now, space has been acknowledged as a domain of military operations, next to the ones of land; sea; air; and cyber. Foremost, space is a physical domain that presents particular properties and challenges but also enables a breadth and depth of defence applications that constitute today indispensable military capabilities. As encapsulated in the words of a former defence minister of France “if space was the new frontier of the 1960s, there is no doubt that today it is a new front on the battlefield.”¹ . If this stands, armed forces should not have any high expectations of winning the next war if they are not capable to be present and active on this front.

In this context, Space ISR deserves the special attention of the defence community and will be presented here by understanding its staging domain; core function; emphasizing its operational value; and by examining the current advancements in technology & applications to acknowledge its competitive edge in today’s military affairs.

2. Space-based Intelligence Surveillance & Reconnaissance

Although the purpose, objectives and functions of space-based ISR remain mostly the same, with its conventional application -as historically proven- in the land; maritime; and air domains, there are also unique advantages and specific limitations while operating from space. The space ISR framework inherits the native properties that come with the particular physics of the near-earth orbital environment; is bound by the maturity level of space technologies; serves the same military objectives on the ground; but is also subject to functional performance characteristics that prescribe its effectiveness at the strategic, operational and tactical level.²

Above all, space offers the highest ground possible for attaining a good observation point. A primeval operational expediency in any conflict, still holding its military value in the era of network-centric, full-digital, all domain warfare. Space ISR allows military actors to see farther, better and more. It reinforces a nation’s defence posture through enhanced situational awareness. This leads to increased deterrence since, friends and opponents alike, understand that there are technical means of verification in place which can see beyond the perceived horizon and detect activities, no

Figure 1: Anatomy of Space ISR: space mission building blocks

matter how deep they are in the strategic hinterland. Capacity in space ISR directly correlates with the level of understanding of the geopolitical landscape and ultimately promotes national security and upholds the prosperity of a country.

ISR is a key enabler for freedom of action and autonomous decision-making while space is a new operational domain for military activities. Together they form an effective framework for comprehensive defence & security at national and collective level.

With space being inherently of global reach; penetrative manner; and of dual-use; space-based ISR is covering drastically the strategic level and recently closing up on lending support to the tactical level. Space ISR comprises a stand-off operational capability, still largely out of harm's way regarding its assets and operators. Space offers ISR the basis for a capability of truly global coverage, without geopolitical restrictions and geographical or regulatory constraints that other domains impose.

In parallel, systems' heritage, battle-proven applications and technological advancements have established today an all-weather and any-light operational capability. Altogether, resilient; cost-effective; scalable; permanently fielded; and always watchful from the best -unobstructed- vantage point one can get;

Space is not fundamentally changing the tradecraft but it has been proven instrumental in enabling consistent and persistent -global wide- ISR, both in reach and effect.

3. The scope of ISR

The purpose of ISR is to improve situational awareness.³ A systematic and coordinated effort to obtain and maintain a current and credible perception of what is the situation at hand. This involves recording, registration, correlation, representation and sense-making of a particular situation.

Conventionally and primarily, ISR is exercised to reveal and apprehend features and activities of military interest that are manifested within the land and maritime domains. This covers the prevailing environmental conditions; presence or absence of anthropogenic objects; actors involved; respective timelines; and monitoring of the evolution of activities;

ISR tries to piece together the most complete picture possible. An iterative, incremental, feedback loop process, entailing multi-view, multi-spectra, multi-time sampling and elaborated knowledge-building all along.

Towards the ultimate goal of delivering gleaned intelligence to planners; decision-makers; & actors; alike. Served through continuous feeds of validated information, on areas of interest and over activities of adversaries. Aimed to understand the dynamics of a particular situation, the interplay of forces in the field, their assumed intentions, and wielded to evaluate the potential and options of all involved actors.

Practically seeking all the answers to the major questions of what is happening when & where; Who does what; and, by deduction and inference, the how and why of actors and effects;

These are the broad objectives of ISR and they lead a perpetual race to detect, identify and track, anything that comes under the scope.

This need for continuous updates and appraisal of our environment and the activities therein has been captured in the concept of the Observe-Orient-Decide-Act (OODA) loop. A widely acknowledged and diversely applicable decision-making and dynamic adaption framework. Conceptualized by a fighter pilot, for all fighters & kinds of fights, it pivots around the survival skill of swiftly adapting and decisively prevailing in contested environments and over highly dynamic situations. The ability to go through the OODA process consistently and keep up with the tempo of operations, effectively determines victory over defeat.⁴ Essentially, the OODA loop describes the way we actually fight, especially after the first bullet flies.⁵

With direct analogy, ISR forms the first half of the Observe-Orient-Decide-Act (OODA) loop by providing dedicated reconnaissance & persistent surveillance (Observation segment) and producing reliable intelligence (Orient segment). Most importantly ISR drives the vector of the whole OODA loop forward, on the basis of factual information and through feedback, which support critically both decision-making and required actions.

In the OODA framework the emphasis is placed on the first two steps of observation and orientation. Respectively, reconnaissance and surveillance have a vigilant role to detect and make out the disposition and dynamics of adversaries. Closing in, from the strategic to the tactical level of operations, the OODA loop gets accelerated as sensor-to-shooter timelines are compressed. While seeking to identify and exploit the opponent's half-beat, speed and timing become complementary and relate with the tempo and fluidity of activities.⁶

Likewise, ISR looks out for the openings that might be exploited as vulnerabilities through the choice of when, where and with what to disrupt the adversary's planning and actions. Ultimately, ISR empowers us to act, with speed, at the right moment, to the exact location and for the maximum effect.

4. The function of ISR

ISR encompasses a set of coordinated and integrated processes that are organized into relevant Concepts Of Operations (CONOPS), according to the level of command and the assets employed. Although ISR applications differentiate across these levels -and depending on the role and capacity of land, maritime, air and space platforms- still, the operational logic is universal and the functionality quite the same.

Expert personnel; dedicated assets; advanced technologies; distributed infrastructure; and orchestrating concepts; all organized into competent ISR frameworks that reliably support military missions.⁷

In this context, the function of ISR:

- Allows to observe a situation systematically (e.g. revisit time of satellites in Low Earth Orbit)
- Deploys, regularly, remote sensing and data acquisition assets to gather raw information (e.g. Optical and SAR satellite imagery)
- Brings back a first-look (e.g. spot/detect a previously unknown object of interest).
- Provides continuous orientation by monitoring the situation at hand (e.g. capture of enemy Order-of-Battle)

- Employs persistent surveillance to reveal patterns and timelines of activity (e.g. over the threshold spikes or absence of activity)
- Keeps up with developments (e.g. Battle-Damage Assessment)
- Produces credible intelligence to support operational command and control (e.g. threat assessment analysis)
- Introduces added value in operations by progressing from raw data to factual information, and from there to actionable intelligence
- Applies analytical processes including Processing; Resolving; Correlating; Fusing; Extrapolating; Modeling; Projecting; Assessing; to make sense
- Installs confidence through informed decisions and by taking knowledgeable action
- Contributes to an assertive defence & security posture
- Reduces the Sensor-to-Shooter timeline

5. Anatomy of Space ISR

At system level, space ISR is based on the operation of dedicated space missions and the exploitation of their image & data output. Space missions are the protagonists here, since they field ISR satellites as orbital platforms for operational use. Like aircraft in the Air Force, ships in the Navy and battle tanks in the Army, satellites in Space Force departments attract all the glory and are the stars of the show. Although space ISR cannot be constructed without the integrating elements of communications networks; payload data ground stations (PDGS); information technology infrastructure; and expert knowledge systems; satellite missions are the pivotal technical means, around which the operational capability is established.

The building blocks of a typical space ISR mission (Figure 1) follow the conventional dichotomy of the space and ground segment sides. The space segment provides the satellite bus, as a platform for fielding the remote sensing payload(s) and includes the launch and communications elements to enable its operations. The corresponding ground segment installs typically the mission control center, with the necessary communications ground network, and - especially for ISR missions- a dedicated PDGS for producing the Analysis Ready Data (ARD) from the satellite raw data acquisitions.

Using a different approach, more along a narrative that observes the cadence of operations, space ISR starts with the last letter of the acronym. Reconnaissance is responsible for providing the space assets as operational capabilities, organic within the military command structure. The U.S. National Reconnaissance Office (NRO) , is the norm setting example of this organizational approach, mandated since the 1960's to develop & operate space missions and to conduct reconnaissance operations from space.⁸

Under the same approach, Surveillance installs the particular regime that applies the operational imperatives to the ISR framework. The dimensions of this framework, like range, resolution, depth and tempo of Surveillance is prescribed by the very own operations' and missions' realities. The framework connects military users with the operational assets through direct tasking or indirect access to the ISR satellites. Surveillance entails persistent information collection activities that require a proliferated space systems architecture to issue, capable of handling joint tasking orders that execute a carefully detailed observation plan.⁹ The full set of systemic image tasking orders, uploaded through mission plan update cycles or ad-hoc events, practically enable operators to task the spacecrafts where to fly and what to record.

In parallel, the function of Intelligence formulates the Requests for Information (RFI), on a need-to-know basis of its actors and according to the objectives of the military and security operations. Intelligence is reactive but also proactive. It responds to users' emerging needs with dynamic tasking of the satellites. It also anticipates informational needs beforehand and plans routine imaging campaigns to keep the space assets effectively busy. On the other hand, Intelligence receives the reconnaissance combined output, fuses this with collateral information and disseminates the final surveillance results through intelligence products & services. By expertly registering & processing, analysing & deducting, and managing data & information, Intelligence is able to generate and disseminate actionable intelligence that seamlessly support almost all military operations & applications.

6. Technology drivers

Space ISR is by name and condition a technologically challenging affair. It resides in the harsh environment of space; it needs to cater for the operational complexity of military doctrines & missions; and it is required to persistently

capture the actual situation and its ensuing evolution, no matter how obscured or hard to reach is the object of interest and despite the change dynamics or divergence from initial assessments & plans.

First of all technology enables ISR to be performed from space. By making possible and available the necessary space and ground systems that can constitute the operational capability in the first place. The anatomy of a space ISR mission has revealed the prerequisite building blocks that correspond directly with high-tech space systems.

In this context, space ISR is enabled by technologies for space systems (i.e. launchers; satellite platforms; power; communications; avionics; propulsion; etc) and for remote sensing payloads (i.e. electro-optical cameras; IR, Hyperspectral, Thermal instruments; SAR imagers; laser & microwave spectroscopy; etc). On the other side, space ISR is made meaningful by systems on the ground that employ Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) (i.e. infrastructure & equipment; data and imagery processing & exploitation; geospatial knowledge information management; visualization; modeling & simulation; security mechanisms; etc) to bring down to Earth the output of the space systems and transform it into strategic value and operational application.¹⁰

Once enabled from space and organized on the ground, advanced technology can further push the range, depth, performances and effect of space ISR through innovation and deep-tech industrial applications.

Contemporary technological trends shape the form and function of space ISR beyond its conventional applications and capacities. In general, the most influential of such technological developments are deemed to be the ones that are now driving advanced materials; extreme miniaturization; AI integration; responsive space concepts; autonomous platforms; optical communications; and quantum applications.

More particular to the ISR operations technologies that lead to low SWaP-C systems (i.e. reduced in Size, Weight and Power & Cost); ubiquitous computing, where all becomes digital and everything is connected with each other; edge-computing and on-board processing (e.g. compression, redaction, fast/first-look reporting); software defined functions (e.g. payload mode switching, processing configuration choice, etc); and Artificial Intelligence for payload operations (e.g. image plan yield optimization), automation (e.g. tip-and-cue tasking) and analytics generation (e.g. unsupervised image data feature extraction);

In this setting and for the near future, technology altogether pushes ISR satellites to fly in constellations & multi-orbits; cover more ground & more often; converge & correlate with differently revealing spectral signatures and signals; respond with agility & operational purpose; and sort out data & filter information at the edge; In parallel and by the same agents, geospatial intelligence work is undergoing a fast paced transformation through technological innovation and paradigm shifts in data & cognitive sciences; big data repositories & cloud computing frameworks; machine learning & AI algorithms on the analysis side; content management & knowledge information platforms; and visualization, modelling & simulation environments.¹¹

7. The competitive edge

The competitive edge of space ISR lies within its primary mission objective, the persistent gathering of data & information and the gleaning of comprehensive intelligence & insights.

Warfare follows the technological, political, economic and societal conditions of its era. While considering that humanity is already in the age of information technology, warfare would need to be effective also in the same setting. The historical shift of the center of gravity in warfare represents this close association. This center of gravity has progressed, along human civilization's transitional steps, from manpower to firepower, onto manoeuvre and by today, definitely into information.¹²

Information is also central in the military discourse about space and ISR, already codified in operational directives and doctrines since the last century.^{13, 14} Space ISR is recognized to contribute drastically in information dominance capability development. The ability to collect data anywhere & anytime; increase information sharing; enable comprehensive cross-domain intelligence; accelerate decision-making & operational tempo; ultimately enhances national and collective defence & resilience postures. Because, a picture is always needed to inform political-decision making and enact military operations.

This becomes the fundamental tenet of ISR, as distilled in the principle of "the right picture at the right time and in the right hands".¹⁵ Although captured within this, appearing to be simple, mandate the actual practice of attaining the right intelligence is an intrinsically complex effort, that involves people; organization; & knowledge; and above all requires significant resources, both in space and on the ground. Space ISR can be improved, in terms of capacity, operational value and -most importantly- cost, through a coordinated approach of wielding, in conjunction, government-owned and commercial space-based systems, applications and data.

Especially if considering that the new space era is here and the agile business models it brings along. Leveraging private funds and public investments it can uptake high-risk projects and fast-track systems, products and services to

the markets. Employing advanced technologies to generate innovative applications; and fielding, any, Capability with as-a-Service mechanism;

ISR can significantly benefit from new space actors since Earth Observation (i.e. the civilian practice of ISR) is an established market with a lot of traction under the boost of new space. The commercially available EO capacity is already exploited the most by defence & security users in ISR since they can easily access technologically advanced space assets; seamlessly integrate credible services of proven operational added value; and acquire, gap-filling, all-spectra, passive & active remote sensing;

ISR can benefit from industrial capacity combined with user-centric business models. The proposition of everything as-a-Service holds promise in the era of big data and all digital frameworks. This has established sustainable industrial activities that develop, field, and operate the high-end EO & ISR satellite systems of today and provision, with credibility, the future generation of advanced ISR space systems.

The technological, industrial and operational proximity & similarity, between Earth Observation and ISR military satellite assets, allows for out-of-the-box synergies and cross-fertilization at the level of systems and applications. All major space applications (i.e. SatCom; EO; & PNT;) are dual-use by design and function. Earth Observation in particular proves this to be true with its established market verticals that are one-to-one corresponding with major defence & security applications in the field of ISR.

By joining forces with EO, ISR can additionally benefit from market investments, leveraging institutional & private funds; and by Private-Public-Initiatives, for pilot & demonstration missions in space that could make operational potentially disruptive capabilities and innovative services.

Ultimately, space is the overarching domain and therein, ISR is one of the primary operational applications. Regarding the state of regional and worldwide geopolitical security and the technological maturity of space systems and applications, military power is severely constrained without space power attributes integrated effectively within the defence & security apparatus at national and collective level.

Space ISR is needed more than ever into the future, to cater for a recognized and consolidated picture that take into account perplexed & combined threats; dense & wide theaters of operations; and force asymmetries & hybrid warfare; In this setting the value of ISR remains in its core function since, recording something is information, visualizing it is perception and making sense out of it is knowledge. Here, space makes ISR a persistent & global; penetrative & unobstructive; and multi-potent & high-performance; stand-off operational capability for maintaining situational awareness in modern warfare.

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Konstantinos Pilaftsis, a former Hellenic Air Force Colonel with 25 years of progressive military experience in Intelligence, Surveillance, and Reconnaissance (ISR) operations, transitioned to a civilian career in the space domain in 2012. Holding an MA in Diplomatic Studies from Westminster University and an MSc in Geoinformatics from the National Technical University of Athens, his expertise spans from analogue to digital geospatial systems, orbital remote sensing, and defense and security space programs. He held senior military roles, including Head of Geospatial Intelligence Analysis for the Hellenic Armed Forces, served as an EU Satellite Centre Expert, and completed UN field missions in Iraq and Sudan. As a former advisor to the Hellenic Government on Space Policy and the first CEO of the Hellenic Space Agency, he significantly contributed to national space initiatives. Currently, he is the Business Development Manager for Defense & Security at Planetek Hellas, leading the OptiSat cubesat mission, and lectures on space, geospatial intelligence, and ISR operations.